

1) Title: Sweet Journey.

In my journey miracles might have been there;
For my journey I need sweet honey;
Commencing my journey without encumbrance;
Leaving my residence with confidence;
Savings withdrawn for my expenditure;
Paving myself for my adventure;
Willing people join with me;
A thrill appears in each phase;
My journey, endless, never concludes;
My savings, countless, never exhaust;
Endless journey makes your life happy;
Surplus money save you fully.

Written by M.J.VENKATESAN.

2) Title: Green Land

I am the Duke of this Province.,
Coming nearby to gratify you.,
My province attains sufficient rain.,
My landscape retains efficient grains.,
Pleasure everywhere persist.,
Pressure nowhere exist.,.
A fortified palace I built in a notified place.,
Just for you.,
Must for your refreshment.,
Best of my creation built with effort.,
I kept the doors always open.,
Enter into my province.,
Entry not restricted.,
Entrance not constricted.,
Dwell upon me.,
Pole star never turns into black tar.,
My greenland never turns bareland.

3) Title: Fast Forward.

**Go, Go, Go, Ho ahead.,
Retraction, never.,
Knockout the rivals.,
Strikeout the rebels.,
Crossover the obstacles.,
Passover dealings.,
Maybe a one-man army.,
Might have been one-man show.,
Do not bother about., go ahead.,
Remember those quotes, frequently.,
Go ahead, subsequently.,
Break the bondage.,
Come out from the linkage.,
Feel free in the battle field.,
Conquer the contest.,**

Never say never again.,

Meet face to face.,

Do or Die; or Die Hard.

4) Title: Femina

Who is he ? What was his motto.,

What he do ? Was this best ?

Let's go to next.,

I can't saw such a whimsical person.,

I want for my theatrical salvation.,

Waiting over a decade.,

Anticipating for a cascade.,

The guy with elevated masculinity.,

Exposing my ethnicity.,

Stimulating my feminism.,

Pronouncing my mysticism.,

Rating my enthusiasm.,

Abstaining me from criticism.

5) Title: Shakespear

I was dwelling in the past, almost thinking of you.,

Come unto me, let us fall in OASIS.,

**I want to explore everything with you, will reach
utmost.,**

Need your presence for succeeding.,

My attitude looks like SAKESPEAR while prattling.,

My gratitude take over control of you.,

Altogether mingling GREENLAND.,

You the unique whom I want.,

Pocessing the physique what I need.,

Searching with expectation.,

Flowers in your towers offers me power.,

Flavours in your glamour glittter forever.